

Forecasting Congestion and Flexibility Needs in the STREAM Project: The sGRID Tool for Distribution Grids

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Abstract—The increasing integration of distributed energy resources (DERs) and electrification of several sectors has introduced new challenges for the operation and planning of distribution grids. These include higher peak loads, reverse flows, and voltage or congestion issues, all of which demand more proactive management strategies from distribution system operators (DSOs) at both medium-voltage (MV) and low-voltage (LV) levels. This paper presents sGRID, a forecasting and simulation tool developed within the Horizon Europe STREAM project to support DSOs in anticipating grid constraints and activating local flexibility. The tool combines short-term load forecasting using XGBoost with topology-based power flow simulations to identify potential violations of grid operational limits. It operates on real grid topologies and integrates weather and smart meter data to generate 15-minute day-ahead forecasts. The tool was validated on a real-world distribution network in Ajdovščina, Slovenia, covering both MV and LV parts of the network. Results show high accuracy for the majority of loads, particularly for large industrial consumers and aggregated transformer-level loads, while also highlighting challenges in forecasting irregular or newly connected consumption points. The findings support the use of forecasting-based congestion detection as a foundation for flexible and data-informed grid operation.

Keywords—Load forecasting, Distribution networks, Congestion detection, XGBoost, Grid simulation, Flexibility

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid integration of DERs, such as rooftop solar and new large loads, is transforming the operation of distribution networks. These changes are making load profiles increasingly volatile, leading to new challenges such as reverse power flows, higher peak demand, and more frequent voltage and congestion issues. Traditionally passive, DSOs are now required to take on a more active role in grid monitoring and control.

A key obstacle to this transition is the limited observability of low-voltage networks. Although smart meters have been widely deployed, their potential remains underutilised. Without timely and accurate information on the state of the network, and more importantly, without the ability to anticipate future grid conditions, DSOs are unable to implement proactive measures.

In this context, local flexibility markets have emerged as a promising solution to alleviate grid constraints and defer costly infrastructure upgrades. However, a critical question remains: how can a DSO determine the amount and location of flexibility needed ahead of time?

The STREAM [1] project, co-funded by the Horizon Europe programme, addresses this challenge by developing a suite of tools to enable local flexibility ecosystems. One of these tools is sGRID, which provides short-term forecasts of grid conditions using historical smart meter data, advanced machine learning models, and weather forecasts. Based on these predictions, sGRID identifies potential constraint violations and communicates them to sSMART, the local flexibility market platform developed within STREAM.

This paper presents the sGRID tool, with a specific focus on its short-term load forecasting capabilities, which serve as a foundation for forecasting grid conditions. The paper details the tool's architecture and forecasting methodology and evaluates its performance on a representative distribution network in Ajdovščina, Slovenia. The aim is to highlight how tools like sGRID can support DSOs' operation of the network and facilitate the transition toward proactive, data-informed grid operation.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Accurate short-term load forecasting (STLF) and congestion prediction are essential for proactive grid operation at the distribution level. These capabilities enable DSOs to anticipate grid constraints and assess flexibility needs in advance.

In load forecasting, early methods such as ARIMA and exponential smoothing were widely used but struggled with nonlinear and highly variable demand profiles. These limitations led to the adoption of machine learning (ML) and deep learning approaches, which are better suited for capturing complex load dynamics. Recent reviews (such as [2]) categorize forecasting methods into traditional, modified traditional, and soft computing techniques, with the latter, including neural networks and fuzzy logic, gaining prominence.

Among ML techniques, XGBoost has emerged as a strong performer for STLF. Studies such as [3] show it outperforms both neural networks and statistical models, particularly when enriched with time-based and weather-related features. Hybrid approaches that combine data decomposition with XGBoost have also been shown to improve accuracy for more volatile industrial loads [4], while ANN-based models remain effective for nonlinear residential demand [5].

While load forecasting provides a foundation, congestion forecasting introduces additional complexity. A hybrid framework in [6] integrates probabilistic power flow simulations with ML-based surrogate models, offering a scalable way to estimate line loadings. Similarly, [7] presents a real-time congestion prediction and control strategy based on gradient boosting and multiscale flexibility coordination, demonstrating improved performance in large distribution networks.

Beyond the academic domain, several tools have been developed to support DSOs in grid forecasting. OpenSTEF [8] offers an open-source forecasting pipeline that combines historical grid data with weather and market inputs for STLF. Its transparency and adaptability make it well suited for utility applications. EnergyHub’s DER Forecasting platform [9] uses real-time measurements from grid-edge devices to deliver high-resolution load forecasts that support congestion mitigation and operational planning.

In addition to these initiatives, related flexibility forecasting and grid monitoring functionalities are being developed in the Horizon Europe OPENTUNITY project [10], where similar techniques are applied to a broader ecosystem of devices including home energy management systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Overview of the sGRID tool

The sGRID tool is designed to support proactive distribution grid operation by forecasting short-term load profiles and simulating power flow to identify potential network constraints. It consists of two primary components: a centralized database and a Python-based simulation engine built using open-source libraries, with pandapower [11] as the core framework for power flow calculations.

The general workflow of sGRID is shown in Fig. 1. The process begins with loading the grid topology model and relevant metadata, including historical smart meter data and weather forecasts. The tool then generates 24-hour load forecasts for all loads in the system. These forecasts serve as inputs to a power flow simulation, which computes key electrical parameters such as line and transformer loading, voltage profiles, and power flows.

The simulation results are evaluated against a set of planning and operational constraints to identify potential violations, such as transformer or feeder overloading. When constraints are identified, the tool estimates the flexibility required to resolve them—specifically, the reduction in load needed to bring the grid back within acceptable operating conditions.

Fig. 1. Workflow of sGRID

B. Grid modelling

The grid topology model used in the sGRID tool was derived from a Geographic Information System (GIS) model of the distribution network, which includes both MV and LV components. The GIS data included essential information such as nodes, lines, transformers, switches, and loads, along with geolocation and electrical parameters like line length, resistance, and reactance.

This data was transformed into a structure compatible with the pandapower library, which represents grid elements as structured data frames for simulation purposes. To reduce computational complexity and improve efficiency, the model was simplified by aggregating the LV networks under most secondary substations into single equivalent loads. This reduction brought down the number of modeled loads from approximately 2,000 to around 150, significantly decreasing the number of load forecasting models required and enabling faster simulation times.

This simplification was guided by the structure of the STREAM pilot, which focuses on an industrial zone where flexibility is being actively tested. The simplified LV networks lie mostly outside this pilot area. As such, their internal structure was not critical to the flexibility analysis and grid forecasting objectives. The effect of these loads on the MV network is still captured, as the total LV demand is preserved and modelled at the transformer level.

Equivalent loads were defined using one of two methods. Where historical measurements were available on the secondary side of the transformer, they were used directly. Otherwise, the load profile was created by aggregating the individual loads beneath each transformer. While this approach limits visibility at the LV feeder level, it maintains the overall load behaviour relevant for MV-level grid forecasting and flexibility identification.

C. Load forecasting

A core component of the sGRID tool is short-term load forecasting, which predicts active power at 15-minute resolution for all loads in the network, including individual consumers and aggregated transformer-level loads.

For this task, we employed XGBoost [12], a high-performance implementation of the gradient boosting algorithm. It is widely recognized for its ability to model structured data efficiently and capture nonlinear dependencies in time-series forecasting problems. The algorithm iteratively builds decision trees to correct residual errors, with regularization mechanisms that help prevent overfitting.

For training, historical smart meter data was used, consisting of active power measurements spanning up to one year and a half per load, where available. The dataset underwent preprocessing to remove outliers, fill missing values, and normalise input variables. An 80:20 train-test split was used to provide initial evaluation model performance on unseen data.

Several features were engineered to support the learning process:

- **Time of day**, encoded using sine and cosine transformations to reflect daily cycles
- **Day of the week**, also encoded as cyclical variables using sine and cosine functions to preserve weekly patterns
- **Day type**, encoded as a binary variable distinguishing workdays from weekends or holidays
- **Month of year**, similarly encoded as cyclical variables
- **Weather data**, including ambient temperature and global solar irradiance, retrieved from the Open-Meteo API

Where possible, up to two years of historical data were used for training. The models were trained using an 80:20 split with the following parameters: maximum depth of 6, learning rate (η) of 0.3, and 100 boosting rounds. Model versioning and storage were handled using MLflow, enabling reproducible deployment during tool operation.

D. Power flow simulation

Once the short-term load forecasts are generated, the sGRID tool performs a power flow simulation to evaluate the anticipated state of the distribution network. The forecasted active power values are used as inputs to the simulation, which is executed using the pandapower library.

Pandapower is an open-source Python package designed for static power flow analysis in balanced networks. In this implementation, the simulation uses a Newton-Raphson solver, configured with a maximum of 100 iterations to ensure convergence even under stressed grid conditions. The simulation produces outputs including line and transformer loading, bus voltages, active and reactive power flows, and total system losses.

Simulation results are then assessed against two types of operational thresholds:

- **Planning limits**, which include safety margins and are used to guide long-term reinforcement decisions.

- **Operational limits**, which define the maximum allowable loading or voltage deviations under normal operating conditions.

By comparing simulation outputs to these thresholds, the tool identifies potential congestion or voltage violations in advance, enabling more informed grid operation.

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the results of the first stage of the sGRID tool's operation, namely the short-term load forecasting for a set of distribution-level loads. The evaluation was conducted on a real-world test case representing the Slovenian pilot site in the town of Ajdovščina. The test grid includes a simplified topology comprising both MV and LV sections, with a particular focus on the industrial park, which features a mix of small, medium, and large industrial consumers. In this area, individual consumer loads as well as aggregated equivalent loads on the LV side of secondary substations are considered.

Forecasting performance was evaluated over a one-week period (from July 8 to July 15, 2024), which was part of the test dataset used during model development. The total number of loads included in the simulation was 139, covering both individual consumer points and aggregated transformer-level equivalents.

To assess forecasting accuracy, we computed two key performance indicators across all loads: the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the normalized mean absolute percentage error (nMAPE). While the model performed well for the majority of loads, a small number of extreme outliers were identified based on their KPI values. To improve the clarity and interpretability of the aggregated KPI visualizations, eight such outliers were excluded from the plots. Specifically, any load with R^2 below -1 or nMAPE above 1.5 was removed, as these values strongly deviated from the rest of the population. This filtering was applied strictly for visualization purposes. The full dataset, including outliers, remains part of the analysis, and one of these excluded loads is examined in detail later in the paper as Case 4.

Fig. 2. shows the distribution of the two primary forecasting performance indicators R^2 and nMAPE across all evaluated loads over the selected one-week period. The R^2 distribution is skewed toward higher values, with the majority of loads falling between 0.6 and 1.0, and the largest group concentrated in the 0.9–1.0 range. This indicates that for a large portion of the loads, the forecasting model was able to capture the variance in the consumption patterns with high accuracy. Only a small number of loads have R^2 scores below zero, which suggests that, in a few cases, the model performed worse than a naive average predictor.

The nMAPE distribution similarly indicates strong performance for most loads, with a peak in the 0.1–0.2 range (i.e., 10–20% normalized error). The tail of the distribution extends beyond 1.0 in a few cases, reflecting loads with either erratic consumption patterns or very low average values, where even small absolute deviations lead to large relative errors. Overall, the distributions suggest that while the forecasting model is generally reliable, a subset of loads remains challenging to forecast.

Fig. 2. Distribution of forecasting performance metrics (R^2 and nMAPE) across all loads.

Fig. 3. illustrates the relationship between R^2 and nMAPE for all evaluated loads. Ideally, the best forecasts are characterized by R^2 values close to 1 (indicating strong alignment with the observed variance) and nMAPE values close to 0 (indicating low normalized prediction error). Loads located in the upper-left quadrant of the plot (those with R^2 between 0.8 and 1.0 and nMAPE below 0.2) represent the highest forecast accuracy, and this is where the majority of the loads are concentrated.

Fig. 3. Relationship between R^2 and nMAPE across all loads in the evaluation week.

Most loads achieve R^2 values above 0.1 and nMAPE values below 0.8, indicating that the model performs reasonably well for the bulk of the dataset. However, a number of outliers are also visible, particularly in the lower-right region of the plot, where both R^2 and nMAPE deteriorate. These cases likely correspond to loads with irregular or highly volatile consumption profiles, where the model struggles to generalize effectively.

To complement the aggregate performance analysis, several individual cases were selected to provide a more detailed examination of forecast behaviour across different types of loads. The selected examples include: a large industrial consumer, an equivalent aggregated load on a secondary substation, a smaller industrial load and one load with poor forecasting performance.

Case 1: A large industrial consumer

Fig. 4 shows the forecast results for one of the largest industrial consumers in the network, with a maximum recorded load of approximately 4,500 kW. Visually, the model tracks the overall shape and daily variability of the consumption pattern well. On Thursday and Friday, the forecast closely follows the actual values, with minor deviations at peak times. The performance is worse on Monday and Tuesday, likely due to irregular startup behaviour following the weekend. On Saturday, the forecast diverges more significantly from the measured profile, which could be due to atypical consumption activity not captured by the features used in the model.

Fig. 4. Comparison of forecasted and measured power for a large industrial consumer over a one-week period

The model achieves an R^2 of 0.83 and an nMAPE of 0.12, indicating reliable performance for this high-impact consumer. From a grid forecasting standpoint, such accuracy is highly valuable, as large industrial consumers are critical for determining loading and congestion risk.

Case 2: Transformer-level aggregated load

Fig. 5. shows the forecasting results for a secondary transformer load with an approximate connected power of 3,500 kW, primarily serving residential consumers. This load is based on control measurements at the transformer level and exhibits highly regular daily patterns, characteristic of household demand. Visually, the forecast aligns very well with the measured data across the entire week.

Fig. 5. Comparison of forecasted and measured power for transformer-level load over one week

The model captures both the daily load shapes and peak timing with high accuracy. The model achieves an R^2 of 0.96 and an nMAPE of 0.04, the highest accuracy among all four cases. The strong performance here highlights the benefits of load aggregation: random fluctuations in individual household behaviour tend to cancel out, resulting in a more stable and predictable overall load profile.

Case 3: Small industrial consumer

Fig. 6. presents the forecast results for a smaller-sized industrial consumer with the connected power of 224 kW. The load exhibits consistent weekday operation with increased consumption during working hours and reduced activity during the night. During the weekend some production activity is present in the load profile, which is successfully captured by the forecasting model. The predicted values align well with the measured consumption, with deviations mostly appearing with sharp load changes or short-term peaks.

Fig. 6. Comparison of forecasted and measured power for a small industrial consumer over a one-week period

The achieved R^2 of 0.89 and nMAPE of 0.12 suggest good model performance, comparable in relative terms to the large industrial consumer in Case 1.

Case 4: Bad forecast example

Fig. 7. shows a case where a model performs poorly, with very low R^2 and extremely high nMAPE. The typical daily pattern for this load consists of negative consumption (i.e., net production) during daytime hours and positive consumption during the evening and night, which remains relatively constant.

Fig. 7. Comparison of forecasted and measured power for a bad forecast example over a one-week period

The model consistently overestimates evening and night consumption and shows mixed accuracy during the production period. Forecasts are occasionally close to actual values (e.g., on Tuesday and Wednesday), but often deviate significantly, especially around sudden changes. The resulting R^2 is only 0.04, and the nMAPE is 50.29, indicating a poor model fit and large

relative errors. From a grid forecasting perspective, such loads pose a notable risk: despite their moderate absolute size, their unpredictability can introduce substantial inaccuracies in simulation results if not properly accounted for.

The poor forecast performance observed for this particular load may be the result of a recent change in operational behaviour or the integration of new energy technologies, such as behind-the-meter generation, which altered the load profile in ways not represented in the historical training data. In this case separate forecast for production and consumption would most likely perform better.

More broadly, across other poorly performing forecasts, several contributing factors have been identified. These include highly irregular or volatile load patterns, measurement anomalies, and insufficient or low-quality historical data—especially in the case of newly connected or rarely active consumers. Addressing these issues will be critical for improving the robustness and reliability of forecasting tools in real-world distribution grid applications.

A. Evaluation of the forecasting results

The results demonstrate that using XGBoost for short-term load forecasting yields strong performance across most loads in the test network. From a grid forecasting perspective, accurate prediction of high-consumption loads is especially valuable, as these have the greatest influence on network behaviour and congestion risk.

It should be noted that the test grid primarily included industrial and commercial consumers. Very few individual household loads were present in this study, as the residential low-voltage part of the grid was only included in aggregated form at the transformer level. Forecasting for individual residential loads is generally more challenging due to irregular behaviour and higher relative variability. However, as seen in the transformer-level case, aggregation significantly smooths the load profile, making accurate forecasting easier and more stable.

Evaluating model performance under real-world conditions involves several challenges. Forecasting errors can arise not only from model limitations or inaccuracies in smart meter data, but also from uncertainties in the input features, such as weather forecasts. Additionally, for small loads, error metrics such as nMAPE can become misleading, returning inflated values when actual consumption approaches zero, even if absolute deviations are small. This highlights the need for careful KPI interpretation when comparing across a wide range of load sizes.

The current approach of training a dedicated model for each load enables tailored learning and generally high accuracy. However, it relies on the availability of sufficient historical data, which may not exist for new or infrequently active connections. For these cases, an alternative is to use generic models, created by clustering historical data into representative load profiles. New consumers can then be matched to the most similar profile, reducing the number of models that must be trained and maintained.

Another key consideration is that load profile evolves over time. Changes in user behaviour, business operations, or the

addition of new technologies (such as PV systems or heat pumps) can significantly shift consumption patterns. As a result, models can become outdated unless they are periodically retrained or adapted using mechanisms that detect changes in load characteristics.

One way to improve robustness is to forecast at higher aggregation levels, such as the MV/LV transformer. As demonstrated in this study, aggregated forecasts are typically more accurate and less sensitive to short-term volatility. However, this approach reduces visibility below the transformer, limiting the ability to detect localized congestion or voltage issues on LV feeders.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented the sGRID tool, developed within the Horizon Europe STREAM project to enable proactive distribution grid operation through short-term load forecasting and power flow simulation. The tool combines machine learning-based forecasting (XGBoost) with load flow analysis using pandapower, allowing DSOs to anticipate potential congestion and assess flexibility needs. The approach was demonstrated on a real distribution network in Ajdovščina, Slovenia, focusing on a mix of industrial and aggregated residential loads.

The results show that the model performs well for most load types, particularly for large industrial consumers and transformer-level aggregates. The analysis also highlighted common challenges such as reduced accuracy for irregular or recently changed loads, and the limitations of some error metrics (e.g., nMAPE) for low-consumption loads. While per-load model training improves accuracy, it also raises issues of scalability and data availability.

Future work will focus on expanding and testing sGRID in operationally relevant scenarios. First, a more detailed evaluation will be conducted, comparing not only forecast accuracy at the individual load level, but also the overall alignment of simulated grid states with real measurements. This will help assess how forecast error propagates at the system level. In parallel, the tool will be integrated with the STREAM project's local flexibility market platform, sSMART. sGRID will be used to identify predicted congestion and quantify the required flexibility, which will then trigger the flexibility auction process. These tests will demonstrate the end-to-end workflow from grid forecasting to market activation. Finally, a simulated environment will be used to explore shorter-term forecasting applications, such as predicting load for the next hour using quasi real-time data. This functionality, while currently constrained by limited access to live grid data, will allow the team to evaluate the potential of near-real-time forecasting for congestion avoidance and intraday flexibility management.

While the current model incorporates seasonal patterns through calendar and weather-based features, their impact on forecasting accuracy has not been studied explicitly. Future work will examine how model performance varies across seasons to improve long-term reliability and generalization.

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